

BASKETBOL O'YIN TAKTIKASINING TASNIFI

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Aniq va tabiiy fanlar kafedrasida o'qituvchisi

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada basketbol o'yin taktikasining tasnifi haqida bayon qilingan.

Kalit so'zlar: Hujum taktikasi, yakka harakat, guruhlar, jamoa, pozitsion hujum, hujum sistemasi, ochko, tezlik va vaqt, shchit, raqib, snayper, "uchlik", "sakkizlik", press, jamoaviy hujum.

CLASSIFICATION OF BASKETBALL GAME TACTICS

Abstract. This article describes the classification of basketball game tactics.

Keywords: attack tactics, Single Action, Teams, team, positional attack, attack system, point, speed and time, shchit, opponent, sniper, "Triple", "Eight", press, team attack.

КЛАССИФИКАЦИЯ ТАКТИКИ ИГРЫ В БАСКЕТБОЛ

Аннотация. В этой статье описывается классификация тактики игры в баскетбол.

Ключевые слова: атакующая тактика, одиночное действие, группы, команда, позиционная атака, система атаки, очко, скорость и время, щит, противник, снайпер, "тройка", "восьмерка", пресс, командная атака.

Taktik tayyorgarlik avvalo har xil ko'rinishdagi kombinatsiyalarni o'rganishni taqoza etadi. Kombinatsiya deganda, basketbolchilardan birining savatga hujum qilish uchun sharoit yaratishga yo'naltirilgan, aniq sistema chegarasida guruh yoki jamoaning hamma o'yinchilari tomonidan ilgari o'rganilgan va o'zaro kelishilgan harakatlar tushuniladi. Bundan tashqari kombinatsiya, tipovoy o'zaro harakatlar, ularning uyg'unligi va yig'ilgan musobaqa tajribalari asosida o'yinchilar tomonidan ijodiy tuzilgan va amalga oshirilgan bo'lishi mumk.

Basketbol taktikasi o'yinini olib borishda qo'llanadigan juda ko'p vositalarga, usullarga va sistemalarga bo'ydir. Jamoalar hujumini yoki himoyani yakka, guruhli va jamoa taktik harakatlari yordamida uyushtiradilar.

Taktika tasnifi

O'yinning asosiy mazmuniga muvofiq taktika hujum va himoya taktikasiga bo'linadi. Uning har bir bo'limi o'yinchilari harakatini tashkil qilish prinsipiga qarab yakka, guruhli va jamoaliga bo'linadi. O'z navbatida, har bir guruh o'yinni olib borish ko'rinishini hisobga olib, ko'rinishlarga bo'linadi (masalan, yakka harakatlar, hujum davomida o'yinchilarning to'psiz harakati va o'yinchining to'p bilan harakati ham bo'lishi mumkin). O'yin harakatlarining aniq mazmuniga qarab ko'rinishlar usullarga bo'linadi. Bajarishning har xil xususiyatlarga ega bo'lgan usullar variantlarining paydo bo'lishiga sabab bo'lishadi. Masalan, markaziy o'yinchi orqali hujum qilish sistemasi pozitsion hujum qilish usullaridan biri hisoblanadi. Bir vaqtning o'zida tayangan markaziy o'yinchilar sonini hisobga olib, bu sistema uchta variantga ega bo'lishi mumkin: bitta markaziy o'yinchi orqali, ikkita va uchta markaziy o'yinchilar orqali hujum qilish.

Hujum taktikasi

To'pni egallagan jamoa hujum qiluvchi jamoa bo'lib hisoblanadi. Hujum qilish jamoaning o'yindagi asosiy vazifasidir. Hujum harakatlari yordamida jamoa tashabbuskorlikni qo'lga kiritadi va raqibni o'ziga bo'lgan taktik reja qabul qilishga majbur qiladi. Hujum qiluvchi jamoaning bosh

maqsadi raqib savatiga to'p tashlashdir. 30 soniya ichida bunga erishish uchun uyushtirilgan ilgaridan o'ylab qo'yilgan va to'pni raqib shchitiga yaqinlashtirishga mo'ljallangan yaxshi tayyorlangan yo'llardan, hujumni bevosita o'tkazish va shchitdan qaytgan to'p uchun kurash imkoniyatini taminlash uchun, shu yakunlovchi kurash uchun qulay sharoitlar tuzishdan foydalanish kerak. Hujum taktikasi, jamoani aniq raqibga qarshi va musobaqaning har xil vaziyatlarida muntazam hujum olib borishning maqsadga muvofiqroq tadbir, usul va formalarini tanlab olish va ulardan foydalanishga imkon beradi. Hujum qilishning hamma harakatlari o'zining xarakteriga qarab yakka (individual) va jamoali hujumga bo'linadi. Taktika tasnifiga muvofiq harakatlar guruhli va jamoaliga bo'linadi.

Yakka (individual) harakatlar

Har bir basketbolchi jamoada bajaradigan vazifasidan qat'iy nazar, hujumda katta faollik ko'rsatishi lozim. Buning uchun u hujum usullarini puxta va malakali egallagan bo'lishi, o'yin sharoitini diqqat bilan kuzatishi, aniq vaziyatga eng mos pozisiya va harakatlarni tez xamda to'g'ri tanlay olishi kerak.

Joy tanlash va himoyachi taqibidan qutilish. To'psiz hujum qilayotgan basketbolchi to'pni qabul qilish, to'pli sherigiga himoyachini taqibidan ozod bo'lishida yordam berishi uchun maydonda ma'lum pozisiyani tanlaydi. Joy tanlash to'htashlar, burilishlar bilan birga yo'nalish malakalarini tezlik bilan o'zgartirib maydonda harakat qilish bilan bajariladi. Savatga tushmay o'tayotgan to'pni ilish uchun joyni to'g'ri tanlash katta ahamiyatga ega.

Ko'rsatilgan usullardan tashqari chalg'itishlar. To'p bilan harakat qilayotgan basketbolchi eng avval himoyachidan qutilishga va savatga to'p otishga harakat qiladi yoki o'ziga bir necha himoyachilarni diqqatini jalb qiladi va himoyachidan bo'shagan sherigiga to'p uzatadi.

To'pni uzatish. Eng asosiysi taktik harakat bo'lib, savatga hujum uyushtirishning natijasi uzatishning yo'nalishiga va o'z vaqtida bajarilganligiga bog'liq. Basketbolchi uzatishdan oldin uning qaysi tomonga va qaysi basketbolchiga uzatilishi lozimligini hal qilish bilan birga mavjud vaziyatda yahshiroq samara keltira oladigan uzatish usulini va vaqtni tanlashi lozim.

To'pni yerga urib yurish. Bu to'pli basketbolchining asosiy yakka joydan joyga ko'chish vositasi bo'lib hisoblanadi. O'yinning o'zgaruvchan vaziyatini kuzata bilish to'pni yerga urib yurushda katta ahamiyatga ega.

Savatga to'p otish. Bu katta mas'uliyat bilan bajariladi, chunki to'p savatga tushmasa, uni raqib egallab olishi mumkin. Basketbolchi har gal savatga to'p otishdan avval o'zining va raqib jamoa basketbolchilarining maydonda joylashishini, shchitga nisbatan o'zining pozisiyasini hisobga olishi, qulay holatni egallashi lozim.

Guruhli harakatlar

Guruhli harakatlar bu nihoyatda zarur taktik ma'lum tipovoy bloklardir, ulardan jamoaning tartibga solingan kombinatsiyon harakatlarining fundamenti yig'iladi. Guruhli harakatlarda o'yinchilarning ijodiy malakalarining birikmalari paydo bo'ladi. Taktik sxemalar uchun ikki yoki uch o'yinchining o'zaro harakatlarining ma'lum usullari universal hisoblanadi.

Ikki o'yinchining o'zaro harakatlari. Ikki o'yinchining o'zaro harakatlarining asosiy usullariga "uzat va chiq" usuli, shuningdek, to'siq to'qnashtirish va kesishlar kiradi.

"To'pni uzat va chiq". O'yinchi to'pni sherigiga uzatadi, keskin yugurish finti bajarib himoyachiga yaqinlashadi, uni muvozanat holatidan chiqaradi, so'ng esa to'g'ri chiziq bo'yicha harakat qilib shchit oldiga chiqadi va savatga hujum qilish uchun to'pni oladi.

“To’pni uzat va chiq” o’zaro harakatning muvafaqqiyatli chiqishi uchun ko’proq yolg’ondakam taktik yo’llardan foydalaniladi. “To’pni uzat va chiq” usuli raqib shchitgacha bo’lgan masofani harakatda bosib o’tish va son jihatdan ustunlik – ikki kishi bir kishiga qarshi 2x1 amalga oshirishda hamda tez yorib o’tish davomida ham keng qo’llaniladi. Ma’lum o’zaro harakatlarda foydalanishning ustunligi ko’pincha basketbolchining shchit tomonga qisqaroq yo’l bo’yicha jasurona, qat’iy keskin yugurushi va raqibning to’sib qolishidan va itarib yuborishlaridan qurqmasdan to’pni olishga tayyorgarligiga bogliq.

To’siq. To’siq mohiyati qoyidagidan iborat: o’yinchi, o’z sherigini ta’qib qilayotgan himoyachi yaqinida shunday qilib joy tanlaydiki, u ta’qib qilayotgan o’yinchini ketidan kuzatishi mumkin bo’lgan qisqa yolni to’sib qoysin. O’yinchi himoyachini harakat qilib o’tishga yo’l qo’ymaydi yoki sherigining yo’liga qaraganda uzunroq yo’ldan harakat qilishga majbur qiladi, hamda o’zi uchun qisqa vaqt ichida ta’qibdan qutilishga va savatga hujum qilishga imkon yaratadi. Bunda to’siq qoygan o’yinchi harakatsiz qolmaydi: himoyachi bilan to’qnashgach u buriladi va hujumga yordam berish uchun shchit tomonga chiqadi. Topli o’yinchi doim to’siq qo’ygandan keyin darhol hujumga kirgan sherigi raqib uchun xavfliroq bo’lishini nazarda tutishi kerak (26-rasm).

Tosiqning uch xili: yondan, orqadan va oldindan qo’yiladigan varianti bor.

Agar to’siq qo’yaotgan sherigini ta’qib qilayotgan himoyachining orqasida yoki yonida joylashsa, unda bu mos ravishda yoki orqadan qo’yilgan to’siq deb hisoblanadi. Uning maqsadi to’pli va to’psiz sherigini kerakli yo’nalishda to’pni urib yurishi yoki kerakli joyga chiqishi uchun ozod qilishdir. Agar to’siq qoytgan o’yinchi, sherigi va uni ta’qib qilayotgan himoyachi o’rtasida (orasida) yuzi yoki orqasi bilan turgan bo’lsa, u oldingi (ichki) to’siq qo’ygani isoblanadi, uning maqsadi – to’pni sherigini savatga to’p otish uchun ozod qilishdir. To’siqdan foydalanib o’yinchi hech qanday qarshiliksiz to’pni savatga otishi mumkin yoki agar ikkala himoyachi ham unga qarshi kelayotgan bo’lsa, to’siq qoygandan keyin tezda raqib shchiti oldiga chiqqan o’yinchiga to’pni uzatish mumkin.

To’psiz o’yinchi uchun to’siqlarni qo’llash, to’pli o’yinchiga qo’llashga nisbatan, ba’zan taktik jihatdan maqsadga muvofiqroq, chunki e’tiborsizroq ta’qib qilishadi (25-rasm).

To’siqqa to’qnashtirish. Hujumchi ma’lum vaqtda static holatda turgan o’z sheriklarining hoxlaganidan, ta’qib qiluvchi himoyachi yo’lida to’siq sifatida foydalanishi mumkin. Sherikning yo’nginasidan katta tezlik bilan yugurib o’tayotib, hujumchi uni ta’qib qilayotgan himoyachini sherigiga yoki himoyachiga to’qnashishga majbur qiladi. Bu bilan hujumchi huddi uni ta’qib qilayotgan himoyachini ko’zlagan pozitsiyada turgan sherigiga to’qnashtiradi.

To’qnashtirishni to’psiz hamda to’pli o’yinchilar bilan amalga oshirish mumkin. To’p olib ketayotgan o’yinchi to’pni uzatib, himoyachini sherigiga to’qnashtirishga erishganidan keyin, undan to’pni qaytarib olish yo’li bilan savatga hujum qilishni yakunlashi mumkin. Bunday holda, to’qnashtirishni uyushtirayotgan o’yinchi to’qnashtirish amalga oshgan zahoti raqib shchiti tomonga tezda chiqishi kerak.

To’qnashtirishning hamma variantlarida asosiysi – raqibni to’qnashtirmoqchi bo’lgan o’yinchi o’z jamoadoshi yonidan unga juda yaqinlashib tez o’tishdir. Bu o’zaro harakatni qiynalmasdan amalga oshirish uchun bir oz oldinroq keskin yugurish finti bajariladi va bu bilan lozim bo’lgan yonalishni (bo’shatib) ozod qilib, himoyachiga yaqinlashadi. Boshqa qator hollarda himoyachilar, to’qnashish natijasida hujumchining savat tomonga yo’lini to’sishga harakat qilib,

ilgariroq o'z shchiti tomon chekinishadi. Unda to'qnashtirishning shchit ostiga chiqish bilan yakunlash ma'noga ega bo'lmaydi. Ikkilanmasdan o'rta masofadan to'pni savatga otish kerak.

“Uchburchak”. Hujumdagi qulay o'yin o'yin vaziyatlari uchburchak bo'yicha o'zaro harakat yordamida vujudga kelishi mumkin. Bunda uchburchakning chuqqisida turgan to'pli hujumchi, oldinga chiqishlari bilan savatga xavf solayotgan boshqa ikki sherigiga qaraganda raqib shchitidan uzoqroq bo'lishi kerak. Kanot bo'yicha harakat qilayotgan o'yinchi to'pni olgach, uni yana sherigiga uzatadi (uchburchak chuqqisiga), to'p u erdan darhol hujumni yakunlash uchun boshqa kanotga yuboiladi. “Uchburchakning” o'zaro harakati uzatishni taz bajarishni talab qiladi: u joyni almashtirish yo'li bilan ham amalga oshirilishi mumkin. Bu o'zaro harakat ayniqsa, hujumchilarning tez yo'rib o'tishida himoyachilar ustidan son jihatidan ustunlikni (3x2) amalga oshirish paytida samaraliroq.

“Uchlik”. Uchburchak holati bu o'zaro harakatda ham saqlanib qolib, to'pni bir tomonga uzatib, hujumning boshqa tomonga to'siq qo'yilishiga asoslangan. Masalan, maydonda 5-o'yinchi to'pni bir tomonga 4-sherigiga uzatayapti, o'zi esa maydonning boshqa tomonida 7-o'yinchi uchun to'siq qo'yapti. To'siqdan foydalanib 7-o'yinchi tezlik bilan jarima zonasiga kiryapti (to'siq qoygandan keyin shchit tomonga chiqqan 5-o'yinchi yordamida) 4-o'yinchidan to'pni oladi va savatga hujum qiladi.

Bu vaqtda, o'rta masofadan savatga to'pni tashlashga yoki to'p yoqotilgan himayani ta'minlash uchun 4-o'yinchi maydon markaziga o'tadi. “Uchlik”ni bajarishda har xil chalg'ituvchi variantlardan foydalaniladi. Masalan, agar 1-himoyachi to'siqdan qochib, jarima otish zonasiga chekinsa, unda 7-o'yinchi yon chiziq bo'ylab raqib shchiti tomoniga keskin yugurishi mumkin yoki 5-o'yinchi sherigi 7-ga o'zining to'siq qoyish maqsadini himoyachilarga ko'rsatib, yarim yo'lda yugurish yo'nalishini o'zgartirish va shchit tomonga 4-o'yinchidan to'pni olish va savatga tashlash uchun shiddat bilan chiqishi mumkin.

“Kichik sakkiz”. Uch o'yinchi to'pni urib yurish bilan birin-ketin kesishishdan foydalanib, shu qatnashchilarning harakat qilgan yo'llari “8” sonini eslatadigan “kichik sakkiz” deb nomlanuvchi o'zaro harakatni bajarishlari mumkin. Usul siklik xarakterga ega va savatga hujum qilish qulay vaziyat kelmaguncha hujumda ketma-ket 4-5 marta qaytarilishi mumkin.

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